

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CASE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article analyzes the differences and similarities of the cases in English and Uzbek in a scientific way

Keywords: Nominative, Genitive, Dative, Accusative, Locative-Ablative.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются различия договоров на английском и узбекском языках в научном ключе.

Ключевые слова: Именительный, Родительный, Дательный падеж, Винительный, Местный Аблатив.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada kelishiklarning o'zbek va ingliz tilida o'xshash, farqli tamonlari ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlari: Bosh, qaratqich, tushum, jonalish, o'rin payt, chiqish kelishiklar

In linguistics, case is a grammatical category that reflects the relationship between a noun or pronoun and other elements in a sentence. In English, case is primarily marked on pronouns, with some remnants of case marking on nouns. There are three main cases in English: nominative (subjective), accusative (objective), and genitive (possessive).

1. Nominative Case:

The nominative case is used for the subject of a sentence, the agent of an action, or the complement of a copular verb. Nouns and pronouns in the nominative case typically do not have any special marking in English, except for personal pronouns. For example:

- She is reading a book.
- They are playing in the park.

2. Accusative Case:

The accusative case is used for the direct object of a transitive verb, the indirect object of a ditransitive verb, or the object of a preposition. In English, pronouns mark the accusative case by changing their form. For example:

- I saw him at the store.

- She gave me a gift.

3. Genitive Case:

The genitive case is used to indicate possession or association between two nouns. In English, the genitive case is marked by adding an apostrophe followed by an "s" ('s) to the noun or pronoun. For example:

- John's car is parked outside.
- The cat's tail is fluffy.

It is important to note that English has lost many of its inflectional endings compared to other languages, leading to a reduction in the overt marking of case on nouns. However, pronouns still exhibit clear case distinctions, which helps maintain clarity and precision in sentence structure.

In addition to these main cases, English also has a few remnants of other cases, such as the vocative case (used for addressing someone directly) and the dative case (used for the indirect object of a verb). While these cases are less prominent in modern English, they can still be observed in certain expressions or archaic forms. Understanding the concept of case in English can help language learners grasp the relationships between different elements in a sentence and enhance their ability to construct grammatically correct and coherent sentences.

On the other hand, Uzbek has a more elaborate system of cases, with six grammatical cases: nominative, genitive, dative, accusative, locative, and ablative. Each case serves a specific grammatical function and indicates the role of a noun or pronoun in a sentence. For example, in Uzbek, the word "kitob" (book) can change its form depending on its case:

- Nominative: kitob
- Genitive: kitobning
- Dative: kitobga
- Accusative: kitobni
- Locative: kitobda
- Ablative: kitobdan

The use of cases in Uzbek allows for more precise and nuanced expressions of relationships between words in a sentence. This complexity can present challenges for English speakers learning Uzbek, as they need to understand and apply the rules of case usage correctly.

Overall, the difference in the case systems of English and Uzbek highlights the diverse ways in which languages structure relationships between words in sentences. Understanding these differences can help language learners appreciate

the unique features of each language and improve their proficiency in using cases effectively.

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